

METHODOLOGY FOR DETERMINING THE EFFECT AND DIRECTION OF DOWNLOADS IN THE PROCESS OF TRAINING A GREEK RUM WRESTLER

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ANNOTATION

This article presents a scientific and methodological assessment of the physical fitness, special physical fitness, functional indicators and load-bearing, size and norm of Greco-Roman wrestlers and shows the results.

Keywords: Greco-Roman wrestling, physical training, special physical training, functional indicators, magnitude of loads, norm, scientific and methodological analysis, scientific methodology, analysis.

МЕТОДИКА ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТА И НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЗАГРУЗОК В ПРОЦЕССЕ ТРЕНИРОВКИ ГРЕКО-РИМСКОГО БОРЦА

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проведен научно-методический анализ физической подготовленности, специальной физической подготовленности,

функциональных показателей борцов греко-римского стиля, определены величина и норма нагрузок, а также показаны результаты.

Ключевые слова: греко-римская борьба, физическая подготовка, специальная физическая подготовка, функциональные показатели, величина нагрузок, норма, научно-методический анализ, научная методика, анализ.

YUNON RUM KURASHCHISINI TAYYORLASH JARAYONIDA YUKLAMALARNING TA'SIRI VA YO'NALISHINI ANIQLASH METODIKASI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada yunon-rim kurashchilarining jismoniy tayyorgarligi, maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligi, funksional ko'rsatkichlari va yuklamalar kattaligi va me'yorini aniqlash yuzasidan ilmiy-uslubiy taxlil olib borilgan hamda natijalar ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yunon rum kurashi, jismoniy tayyorgarligi, maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarligi, funksional ko'rsatkichlari, yuklamalar kattaligi, me'yor, ilmiy-uslubiy taxlil, ilmiy uslubiyat, tahlil.

Introduction The relevance of the topic believes that high indicators of the functional capabilities of athletes directly depend on the number of training sessions taking place in the microcycle and on the day, and the Reserve capabilities of the body to solve the task of basic and additional training are maintained at the level necessary for it.

Analysis of the literature on the topic L.P.Matveev Belov A.V, and others mainly advance two main factors: the effect of loads on the state of athletes and the rational exchange of loads of different sizes during the training process. Today, in sports practice, there are not enough scientifically based guidelines and recommendations regarding the problems of the influence of loads of different sizes

and directions on the state of wrestlers in sports wrestling. An analysis of available sources has shown that in their scientific work it is necessary to influence the special endurance components of wrestlers on a competitive basis.

Research methodology his scientific work reveals ways to raise the aerobic and anaerobic capabilities of wrestlers and gives practical recommendations for its implementation.

Table 1
Methods for determining the effect and direction of downloads in the training process of Greek rum wrestlers (n-16)

Tajriba guruhi	10 seconds	13	15	17	19	22	23	27	31	26	22	29	27	25	30	32	28	23	19	14
	1 min.	78	90	102	114	132	138	162	186	156	132	174	162	150	180	192	168	138	114	84
	Training effect	KE	KE	KE	KE	KE	KE	AA A	AG	AA A	KE	AA A	AA A	KE	AA A	AG	AA A	KE	KE	KE
	Scoring points	5	3	1	1	4	5	10	21	8	4	14	10	7	17	25	12	5	1	4
	Exercise time	6	5	7	5	4	4	6	6	10	5	8	6	7	4	4	5	8	8	12
	Total download size	30	15	7	5	16	20	60	126	80	20	112	60	49	68	100	60	40	8	48
Total load size																				924

Note: KE is more aerobic, AAA-mixed arob-anaerobic, AG-anaerobic glycolytic. The overall payload size was 924. By multiplying the evaluation score and exercise performance time, the total load size and total load size were developed.

Methods for determining the effect and direction of downloads in the training process of Greek rum wrestlers

Heart contraction experimental groupinig results showed that heart contraction in this was determined by 10 seconds and measured 19 times during the 120-minute training period, the results of the overall group were determined, and in this the results of the experimental group of Greek rum wrestlers, in which no specific movements were detected during the training period.

The purpose of the study in his scientific work, the solution of this problem is considered from a different point of view. The use of Special Non-economy medium-sized loadings in training has extended the decrease in the effect of alternating loadings by 2-3 days. The use of a load in a special description of the same size extends the recovery period of the organism by 4-5 days, according to the author, the duration of

the recovery of special endurance does not depend on its direction, but on the size of the next load.

Results and discussions according to the most recent research work carried out in other sports, in particular, the reduction of the body's recovery period after the use of large loads in sports wrestling types differs according to the size and direction of loads, and the effectiveness of the recovery process increases only under conditions when the size and direction of loads in additional training differ from despite the fact that the use of loads of different sizes and directions in Greek rum wrestling training is very important in solving the problem, the problem of their impact on the body and state of athletes has not been solved. There is not enough information on this problem, including in the available sources. This testifies to how relevant the problem under study is. Our research is also devoted to this problem.

High load training is a major factor in raising the working capacity of highly qualified athletes. Boltayev Z.B, states that after the moment the athlete reaches the peak of a certain level of conditioning, further development of his physical qualities can be achieved only if he can apply the highest loads in accordance with his personal functional characteristics. A large number of authors argue that the use of large-load training in the pre-competition preparatory stage provides great benefits. At the same time, in accordance with the results of another study improper planning of large-load training leads to a violation of the lifestyle, diet, work and rest rhythm, and extreme strain occurs in the athlete's body.

Volkov V.N. and others show that the emergence of such a state of extreme tension is also influenced by a violation of the principle of solitary exercise.

However, Guba V.P, (35) believes that an increase in the functionality of the athletes ' organism will be associated with an increase in the level of conditioning of the athlete. In accordance with the above points, it can be concluded that the performance of large-load exercises in the training process is the main factor indicating the degree of impact on the body of athletes. As a result, the higher the speed and intensity of recovery processes in the body of athletes, the higher the load size.

Dorohov R. According to the opinions of N, (100), training with a large load changes the following functional indicators of the body: exhaustion in the muscles, difficulty breathing, decreased ability to work and activity, decreased sensitivity, the appearance of general exhaustion, rawness, decreased attention, difficulty in thinking processes, etc. Based on the analysis of the above signs, it can be concluded that it is impossible to determine the nature of the load, the magnitude of the load in training in accordance with the body's response movement. After applying super-high loads in

training, up to 4-6 days the body's working capacity will be higher than its initial state (level). Planning a repeat of downloads on the same days will give a good result. In studies with players, however, the ability to work like this has been maintained for up to 7 days. After the application of large loads, the duration of the recovery period of the body stretches from 3 to 8 days.

Kerimov F.A. The result of studies (47) shows that after the application of large loads, after 2 days, a slight recovery (supercompensation) effect of disturbed balance may appear in the body, but during the first day there is a strong decrease in the body's working capacity. In his research, from training conducted with large loadings, he studied the improvement of the special endurance phase for a long time. The author believes that the effect of downloads at a long stage of training depends on the description of the work to be performed next.

A number of authors believe that in addition to greatly increasing the recovery effect of disturbed balance in the body, it is necessary to apply loads that contribute to a certain level of recovery in future training. In several other research works (108,120) this topic is also developed. The authors attach importance to large-load training, which is carried out in case of recovery, which is not enough to increase the results of more sports. They argue that the disturbed balance in the body depends on the condition of performing a large load of work in the fatigue phase - before a state of yet unimaginable recovery occurs.

Such a phase is assumed by large loads up to 30-50% of the total volume of work performed in individual training. The severity of the loads the subsequent preservation of the effect will depend on the movement voltages in the body and its vegetative functions. This stage is a necessary moment to increase the functionality of the athletes' organism in the process of training. We know that according to most studies various processes have occurred in the body as a result of muscle work activity, and they can be divided into phases as follows: 1-exhaustion; 2-Recovery; 3-Extreme recovery; 4-return to the initial state. In the process of training, it is necessary to achieve that the trace of the effect generated in the body under the influence of loads does not completely disappear before giving a new load. The loadings given in this case are transformative in nature, and as a result of prolonged muscle work activity, traces of the effect are formed in the body.

Conclusions and recommendations As a result of muscle work activity, functional and structural changes occur in the body, as a result of which it leads to an increase in the level of training rhythm. According to the results of the study, they propose to divide the recovery phase of the organism into 2 interconnected phases:

Phase 1 is the initial recovery, which can take from a few minutes to several hours. This is the case (the restoration of the body's working capacity due to changes in somatic and vegetative functions will have a homeostasis orientation); phase 2 – constructive changes in the systems and tissues of the body (conditions are created for the formation of a response reaction). The second phase plays a key role in creating the body's chances of being able to handle large physical loads. Therefore, work and rest performed in the structure of microcycles are of particular importance.

Nevertheless, it is difficult to imagine increasing the level of exercise without large loads, when planning microcycles, it is also necessary to include the initial period of work between sessions. During the same period, conditions are created to give the response reaction of the organism, which is necessary for a positive termination of constructive plastic processes.

LITERATURE

1. Керимов Н.А. Программированное обучение технико-тактическим действиям в спортивной борьбе: Автореф. дис. канд. пед. наук. - М.,1990. -24 с.
2. Керимов Ф. А. Спорт сохасидаги илмий тадқиқотлар. Тошкент, 2018.- 334 б.
3. Керимов Ф.А. Методика обучения сложным технико-тактическим действиям в вольной борьбе: Автореф. дис. канд. пед. наук. – М., 1984. – 24 с.
4. Керимов Ф.А. Спорт кураши назарияси ва услулияти. Т.: Илмий техника ахбороти-пресс нашриёти, 2018.-С. 188-190.
5. Керимов Ф.А. Спорт сохасидаги илмий тадқиқотлар //Спорт сохасидаги илмий тадқиқотлар. – Т.: «Zar qalam. – 2018. – 334 б.;
6. Керимов Ф.А. Теоретико-методические направления содержания и структуры дисциплины спортивной борьбе: Автореф. дис.д-ра пед.наук. – М., 1995. – 53 с.
7. Керимов Ф.А. Якка кураш элементларига эга бўлган харакатли ўйинлар. Т.: Илмий техника ахбороти-пресс нашриёти, 2020.-79 б.
8. Керимов Ф.А., Умаров М.Н. Спортда прогнозлаштириш ва моделлаштириш. - Т.: ЎзДЖТИ, 2005.- 279 б.